

The Reality of Applying the Crisis Management Approach in the Egyptian Ceramic Companies

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Abstract: This study aimed to identify the application of the crisis management approach in ceramic companies in the Tenth of Ramadan City, where the researchers used the descriptive analytical method, through a questionnaire that was distributed. The study reached a set of results, the most important of which are: The results clearly indicated the approval of the study sample from the members of the senior management that all of these elements are well applied in the ceramic companies under study. On the stages of the crisis clearly applied in the ceramic companies under study, the study sample of workers in the companies agreed on average on all elements of the strategy to change the direction of the crisis and that it was not applied in a significant way, the study sample of employees agreed to a certain extent on all elements of the crisis division strategy and the strategy Containment of the crisis and that it is widely applied. The study sample of workers agreed in an average way on all elements of the crisis management strategy and that it was applied in a non-significant manner. The approval of the study sample of the workers in a large extent on all the elements of the stage of signals and early warning and that they are applied in a small way, and finally the approval of the study sample of the workers in an average way on all the elements of the stages (damage containment, recovery of activity, learning) and that they are applied in an unclear and inappropriate manner. The study presented a set of recommendations, the most important of which are: the need for companies to be convinced of the importance and usefulness of having a crisis plan, working on developing basic steps for the crisis planning process, forming a crisis management team and selecting it efficiently, the need to address crises by working with plans. Training and preparing individuals to perform efficiently and effectively in crisis situations.

Keywords: Crisis Management, Ceramic Companies, 10th of Ramadan City, Egypt.

Introduction

Ceramic companies in the Tenth of Ramadan City are among the labor-intensive industries, with huge capital, which contribute significantly to increasing state revenues through taxes, reducing unemployment rates through employment, increasing growth rates in this sector, and bridging the gap between ceramic needs and the Import to save foreign currency.

And through the pursuit of these companies to achieve success in their activity to build a distinguished strategic and competitive center that guarantees them survival and growth, they also seek to improve their performance according to the environment in which they arise by adapting to environmental changes and factors, and benefiting from them in order to know what threats and crises they face and how to Reducing its severity and seizing available opportunities, and how to take advantage of them.

Problem Statement

Interest in the approach of crisis management in companies is increasing due to its far-reaching effects on the future and survival of the company, as man has become able to cause disasters of greater magnitude than natural disasters, and if we can predict some natural disasters, we cannot prevent them, all we can do It is preparing to face these crises and disasters. As for man-made crises and disasters, they can be predicted, and they can also be prevented or prepared for. These indicators and phenomena were represented through the exploratory study, and the problems can be identified as follows:

1. The emergency plan that was prepared by the ceramic companies in the tenth of Ramadan depends on the reaction in the confrontation after the occurrence of the crisis or accident.
2. The inability to accurately determine who is responsible for crises in companies, which hinders the final resolution of crises.
3. The predominance of the concept of industrial security instead of crisis and disaster management.
4. Weak means of communication and coordination between crisis and disaster response agencies.
5. The lack of clarity of the concept of crisis management, its stages and strategies in the minds of those who prepare emergency plans and procedures for the different sites in the companies.
6. Focusing on technological and environmental crises and neglecting other crises (psychological-economic, information...) that cause sit-ins and strikes among workers.

Through the foregoing and based on differences between the results of previous studies and the aforementioned phenomena, the researchers can say that the research problem is the lack of clarity of the concept of crisis management, its strategies and its stages

for all workers in the ceramic sector in the Tenth of Ramadan City, which negatively affects the improvement of organizational performance in those companies. Thus, the problem can be formulated in the following question:

What is the reality of applying the crisis management approach in ceramic companies in the Tenth of Ramadan City?

Research Objectives

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Activating the stages of crisis management before, during and after the crisis to obtain planned results to increase the performance level of ceramic companies in the Tenth of Ramadan City.
2. Adopt the indicated crisis management strategies to implement the plans to obtain the planned results.
3. The need to establish a crisis management unit in the organizational structure of ceramic companies and to use an efficient crisis management team.
4. Rooting the intellectual and philosophical framework for crisis management.
5. Suggesting a set of recommendations that contribute to the efficiency and effectiveness of crisis management stages and strategies in ceramic companies in the Tenth of Ramadan City.

Research Importance

The aspects of the study's importance can be identified from the contribution and expected addition from it, as follows:

Scientific (Theoretical) Importance:

1. Through this research, it is possible to identify how to choose or determine the material and human capabilities to ensure the implementation of crisis management plans in the sector under study.
2. Through this research, it is possible to identify the files of previous crises in the ceramics industry, the methods used by the crisis management to confront them, and the results of those methods.
3. This research contributes to increasing the effectiveness of crisis management to contribute to preventing potential crises and preparing to respond to them if they occur in the sector under study.

Practical (Applied) Importance:

1. The current research is due to the importance of the applied field, where the field study is carried out on the ceramic sector in the tenth of Ramadan city, which is one of the pillars of the national economy. Minimizing its negative effects and benefiting from the positive effects in the process of improving organizational performance in ceramic companies.
2. The ceramic sector faces many economic, administrative, and organizational crises and crises resulting from human errors. The most important crises are workers' strikes, which affected the suspension of production lines in those companies. The workers' demands were to increase their salaries, and the payment of annual profits by 10%, the exchange of a normal work allowance and shifts, the payment of a risk allowance, Disbursing a meal allowance, health insurance to include the rest of their families, which requires the ceramic sector to establish a crisis management unit in the organizational structure of companies.
3. The ceramic sector is characterized as a labor-intensive society, and a high rate of risks faced by workers in this sector, and is characterized by rapid turnover of work, and is characterized by material and moral benefits for workers.
4. The research also derives its importance from the expected results that may contribute to supporting the industrial environment of the business organizations in question so that this is reflected positively on crisis management.

Research Limits and Scope

The scope of the study shall be as follows:

1. **Objective Limits:** The study focused on identifying the reality of applying the crisis management approach in ceramic companies in the Tenth of Ramadan City.
2. **Human Limits:** The study was conducted on senior management and workers in ceramic companies in the Tenth of Ramadan City, who responded by filling out a questionnaire.
3. **Institutional Limits:** The field study was conducted on the ceramic industry sector, which includes (five major industrial companies) for ceramics in the Tenth of Ramadan Industrial City.
4. **Spatial Limits:** The study was conducted in the Arab Republic of Egypt.

Previous Studies

- Study of (Abu Amuna et al., 2017) The study aims to analyze the relation between strategic Environmental Scanning and crisis management in UNRWA- Gaza Strip field - Palestine. Several descriptive analytical method used for this purpose, and a survey as a tool for data collection. Community population was (881), and the study sample was stratified random (268). The overall findings of the current study show that strategic Environmental Scanning is conducted in UNRWA and has a stoical relation with crises management. This relation is weak and need to be strengthen especially during and after the crisis. The study suggest that strategic Environmental Scanning must be conducted permanently for external and internal environment to help UNRWA developing its strategic planning and to be to prepared to deal with potential crises in the future.
- Study of (Al Shobaki, M. J., et al., 2016) aims to study the role of strategic and operational planning as approach for crises management in UNRWA - Gaza Strip field- Palestine. Several descriptive analytical methods were used for this purpose and a survey as a tool for data collection. Community size was (881), and the study sample was stratified random (268). The overall

findings of the current study show that strategic and operational planning is performed in UNRWA. The results of static analysis show that there are a relation between strategic and operational planning and crises management. In spite this relation existence, it need more improvement and expanding. Also there are shortcomings in the way that organization manages the crises before and after they occur. A crisis management is only practicing during the crisis.

- Study of (Al Shobaki, M. J., et al., 2016) aims to analyze the impact of top management support for strategic planning on crisis management in UNRWA-Gaza Strip field in Palestine. Several descriptive analytical methods were used for this purpose, and a survey as a tool for data collection. Community size was (881), and the study sample was stratified random (268). The overall findings of the current study show that top management provides needed HR for strategic planning but with no financial support. Also there are shortcomings in the way that organization manages the crises before and after they occur. A crisis management is only practicing during the crisis. The study suggest that top management must provide the financial support for strategic planning, periodic meetings to prepare how to deal with potential crisis in the future, establishing a specialized team and provide them with all sources needed.
- Study of (Al Shobaki, M. J., et al., 2016) aims to identify the impact of the strategic orientations (Vision, Mission, goals) on crisis management agency, international relief in Gaza, the researchers used the descriptive and analytical approach and a survey for collection data, amounted to community size (881), and the study sample (268), and the sample was a stratified random. SPSS program used for entry, processing and analysis of data. The most important findings of the study: The results showed that the organization develop a clearly written vision, mission and strategic goals and the organization's strategic objectives are consistent with the vision and mission of the organization. The results also showed that the organization develop a clear stage objectives framed with time bass which can be achieved on the ground. The employees in the organization's behavior comes within a disciplined set of principles and values that underpin the organization. Also the concept of the organization vision and mission are familiar for the employees. In general the views of the research sample agreed that there is a presence of strategic orientations (vision, message, goals). A direct positive correlation between the presence of strategic orientations (vision, mission and goals) and crisis management (before, during and after the crisis) in the international relief agency in Gaza.
- Study of (Zenica-Livia et. Al., 2012), which aimed to identify the literature and concepts of changing moral behavior in times of economic crises, and was applied to Romanian organizations, where the sample size was 265 employees who answered the two survey models, the first designed to identify the reasons that Lead to unethical behavior during economic crises The second is designed to identify procedures to prevent unethical behavior during economic crises. The study showed that in the occurrence of crises, five reasons emerge for the lack of ethical behavior, the most important of which are: wage cuts, loss of benefits and a feeling of job loss, which puts workers under enormous pressure, which becomes a motive for making any gains at the expense of ethical standards in their behavior. The study concluded that the most important measures to prevent unethical behavior are training managers and employees and developing their culture, especially in the first year of their membership in the facility, to instill ethical standards and prevent the basis of unethical behavior that may result from economic crises.
- Study of (Thomas & Charles, 2011), which aimed to identify how to develop models based on crisis management (crisis scenarios) in order to confront organizational crises, where a sample of American industrial institutions was selected to conduct this study and reach results that can be blinded to most American industrial organizations. . The most important results of the study were that simulating crisis scenarios was the ability to increase insight into organizational structures as needed according to the escalation of crises. The development of communication with the organization is one of the important factors for success in managing organizational crises, as the time factor is one of the important factors that help in managing crises efficiently.
- Study of (Medien, 2010), which aimed to identify the important role of integrated communications during organizational crises, as this represents a modern approach to managing organizational crises. The study highlights modern technical methods in communications that help in managing organizational crises, and that support leadership in making efficient decisions during a crisis. The study concluded that there is a relationship between integrated communications and managing the organizational crisis successfully, as all marketing, financial, technical and human systems are integrated so that their outputs represent an integrated communications model that helps to confront organizational crises and manage them efficiently. The study called for the importance of timely media communication when a crisis occurs, as this helps to overcome and address it quickly, and the media spokesperson has an important role within the crisis team, where he must be one of its members.

Commenting On Previous Studies: After reviewing the most important previous studies related to the subject of the current study and reviewing and analyzing the results of those studies, the researchers were able to derive the following elements:

Elements of Crisis Management: Some studies have focused on identifying some of the elements of effective crisis management, and this is represented in:

1. All previous studies mentioned in the field of crisis management agreed that having a good information system, as well as a good communication system, is one of the necessary ingredients for the success and effectiveness of crisis management in any company, and that the low effectiveness of communication systems in providing accuracy, speed and fluidity required for information exchange represents One of the most important obstacles to crisis management.
2. The study of (medien, 2010, Thomas, 2011, Zenica 2012) agreed on the importance of integrating integrated communications and successful crisis management, as all marketing, financial, technical and human systems are integrated so that their outputs represent an integrated communications model that helps to confront and manage organizational crises efficiently, as well as

Media communication in a timely manner when the crisis occurs, and that the media spokesperson has an important role for the crisis management team.

Similarities and Differences with the Current Study: The similarities or differences between this research and previous studies, where the study agrees with the study (Taneija, 2014), is the necessity of integrating crisis management within the strategic management of the organization so that the impending crises are prepared and prevented by identifying the factors that lead to crises through studying and analyzing the internal and external environment of the organization and taking Actions to deal with it. The study relied on dividing crisis management into crisis management stages, which are divided into (the stage of early signs and warning, the stage of preparedness and prevention, the stage of damage containment, the stage of recovery of activity, and the stage of learning).

As well as to crisis management strategies (the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis, the strategy of assessing the crisis, the strategy of containing the crisis, and the strategy of dealing with the crisis).

Theoretical Framework

Crisis Management: Crisis management has recently become one of the important components of management in any organization, and these days there is no organization far from crises (Gad El-Rub, 2010, P: 224), and crises are considered unpleasant to the soul, because they make you feel instability and sudden change of what they feel Confusion, anxiety, and perhaps impulsive and hasty decisions that make matters worse (Aeje, 2008). Therefore, dealing with crises is one of the axes of interest in management, as it requires the presence of a special type of managers who are characterized by many skills, including: courage, consistency, balance, the ability to think creatively, and the ability to communicate and dialogue (Ibrahim, 2002, P: 32).

1. **The Concept of Crisis Management:** Modern organizations are recently faced with pressures and challenges represented by the continuous increase of internal and external forces affecting their stability and profitability. It is up to governments and management organizations to make arrangements to confront such challenges and to strengthen their competitiveness (Abdel Salam, 2001, P: 11).

The crises have caused great losses and severe economic damage, affecting the lives of hundreds of organizations around the world. These crises are undoubtedly major obstacles in the way of the development and development of these organizations. Addressing these crises requires that crisis and risk management be included in the development plans of countries and organizations. Both rely on a developed knowledge base and awareness of decision makers (Gadallah, 2008, P: 10).

There are many concepts that define crisis management, including the definition (Suresh & Goel, 2009) as a system that is applied to avoid emergency situations and how to deal with them when they occur, in order to mitigate their devastating effects. (Rudwall & Larson, 2012) defined crisis management as “a group of functions or Processes for identifying, studying and predicting the issue of a crisis” and also known as “the process by which warning signs are identified in order to reduce the occurrence of a potential crisis” (Sekeroglu. o, Yamamoto. G, P. 32), and sees (Gad El-Rub, 2011, P: 106) “Crisis management is a series of specific activities and procedures carried out by the senior management in the organization from three entrances:

Crisis prevention, crisis preparedness at the time of its occurrence, post-crisis measures.” In another definition, it is “a purposeful activity based on research and obtaining the necessary information that enables management to predict the locations and trends of the expected crisis and create the appropriate climate to deal with it, by taking the measure to control the expected crisis and eliminate it or change its course in favor of ”.

Through the previous concepts of crisis management, its elements can be identified as follows:

- It is a special administrative process represented in a set of exceptional procedures that go beyond the usual job description for administrative tasks.
- Those in charge of crisis management must have the capabilities to make decisions quickly, and have specially trained competencies in facing crises.
- Crisis management aims to reduce losses to the extent possible.

2. **Stages of Crisis Management:** The crisis passes through its inception and completion cycle in several basic stages that show its chain of development from its beginning as an accident until confronting it and starting to deal with it. It should be noted that no matter how different the views of the researchers on the stages of the crisis are in the nomenclature, but there is no difference in content. And crisis managers should look at the stages of the crisis with a high concentration in order to be able to meet the challenges and needs of the administration represented by different and vital dimensions in each stage (David, 1994, P. 300).

The stages of the crisis are intended to divide the crisis management function into separate sectors of a certain arrangement.

Coombs (2007) divided the stages of the crisis into three stages according to the time basis:

- **Pre- Crisis Stage:** It begins by focusing on early warning detection and prevention by preparing teams, analyzing the situation, gathering facts and training staff.
- **Crisis Response Stage:** At this stage, the crisis is dealt with and how to rebuild the reputation of the organization or the individual, as a result of the organization's exposure to damages that are known and attempted to be dealt with.

- **Post – Crisis Stage:** It is preparing for the next crisis, and fulfilling all the commitments made during the crisis stage, including providing follow-up information, and a radical change may occur at this stage after the crisis is over. A number of researchers have relied on this division, including (Robert. M, 2010), (Lai, 2010).
 - 3. **Crisis Planning:** The goal of crisis planning is to increase the efficiency of the crisis management team and all the officials in the organization, especially the senior management, in managing the crisis, during the occurrence of crises or disasters and calamities whatsoever. Increasing the efficiency of these parties reduces the negative effects of the crisis and maximizes the positive effects and opportunities resulting from it. On the other hand, crisis planning leads to predicting crises before they occur and preparing for them from various aspects and in all productive, financial, marketing, security and other activities. Some managers believe that crisis planning is unnecessary, while a large number of them see that developing a crisis plan is one of the things. The strategy in the organization and its most important core responsibilities (Gad El-Rub, 2010, P: 151-152).
 - 4. **Stages of The Crisis Planning Process:** Business organizations must be convinced of the importance and usefulness of having a crisis plan, but the understanding of the importance of crisis planning varies according to the importance and efficiency of the objective plans and those in charge of the planners. For all crises, it is a complex matter that represents a difficult, arduous and stressful challenge that has its core (Gad El-Rub, 2010, P: 151-152).
 - 5. **Basic Steps of The Crisis Planning Process:** Researchers present five basic components or steps of the crisis planning process. These steps or stages are:
 - **Crisis Team:** Any successful business organization finds it has a strong management team and finds it has an efficient and effective financial position, and the effective formation of the management work team leads to the achievement of successful financial results for any organization, and therefore, individuals who join the crisis team must be selected efficiently, not with the aim of succeeding in crisis management, but With the aim of maintaining the organization's survival in the business world.
 - **Analyze Vulnerabilities:** The full and accurate analysis of all crises that are likely to attack the organization is a difficult and complex process, but it is necessary and essential.
 - Managers can list three or four crises the organization faces such as fire, floods, outage crises, hurricanes or other natural disasters.
 - With the cooperation of these managers with the risk departments of the organization, a list of the negative and positive effects of crises can be drawn up, with a worst case scenario, Work Case Scenario.
 - These events that result in crises must be of importance and have a strategic priority and need organizational strategies to deal with them.
 - **Create Strategies:** Once a list of potential crises has been developed, the crisis team can begin to work on developing comprehensive strategies to avoid crises or to mitigate their effects and events. As is the case when developing any strategy, the team's role is not to develop, create or compose accurate detailed plans, but rather focuses on general goals and expectations, especially in the long-term of crises, and then the functional levels implement these plans or strategies, where there is a working team Or an operational group in each department that takes all the detailed measures to cover the losses or disasters resulting from the events of the crisis and in light of the general objectives of the crisis team's plan and strategy.
 - **Work the Plans:** In light of the foregoing, an effective crisis team is developed, formulated and formed, and this team develops a comprehensive planning strategy for the crisis, until then comes the efficient implementation of this strategy through the functional levels in the organization, with training and preparation of individuals to perform efficiently and effectively in crisis situations, to ensure that Any crisis can be avoided or its effects mitigated by Mitigate. At this stage, the wisdom and experience of both the crisis team and qualified personnel are of great value, and organizations must work the plan, but through support and flexibility in order to adapt and harmonize with the various requirements of the event, and when adaptation is difficult, the crisis team must record deviations, including the logic and returns of changes That is difficult and held with the process of adapting the plan.
 - **Assess Performance:** Sometimes plans are implemented in a failed and painful way for the organization, or vice versa, the success is amazing, so some lessons must be learned from analyzing actual performance compared to the expected performance from crisis plans, and if a harmful failure occurs in the plan, it is important to ask why and how the deficiency is identified and treated in the future. In this regard, the researchers asked the responsible managers of ceramic companies about the steps taken to plan for the crisis. The senior management responsible for planning for the crisis made it clear to abide by the planning steps through the scientific method used in crisis planning, as well as to exploit all its human and material resources available to confront crises. The researchers found, by discussing the leaders, that companies do not depend in the planning process on the executive management or any other management in developing crisis management plans, and there is weakness in the process of training programs in the field of crisis management. Companies must participate with all the departments concerned with the crisis in planning it and quickly build the organizational structure for crisis management and follow all steps and study the causes of the crisis and build a crisis management model capable of facing crises according to the plans of its subject.
- Crisis Management Team:** No organization can prevent all crises from happening, but the most important thing is that a crisis management team is available that makes the university organization able to prepare for any crisis in all respects in full swing and train on it, as well as deal efficiently and effectively with crises as well as benefit from them after their occurrence. Determining a

crisis management team is included in the organization as an important crisis management process, in which the people entrusted with the special work of crisis management, the tasks associated with each of them, the activities that they will undertake to manage the crisis, and who will be responsible, and the means of communication, are identified, and this varies according to the size of the organization and the severity of restrictions in it (El Hamlawy and Shoman, 2002).

What is meant By the Crisis Management Team: It is the group selected from the university organization according to previously confirmed experiences, which undertakes a flexible and purposeful dealing with various expected and unexpected crises before, after and during the occurrence. This team may be three people in small organizations and may reach dozens in large organizations and these teams are more democratic than others from other committees or teams, they do the following (Abbas, 2004, P: 74):

- Contact the responsible person when an alarm signal appears.
- Develop a crisis prevention plan.
- Training and educating employees on plans to prevent and confront crises.
- Prepare crisis management plans.
- Follow up on its implementation when the crisis strikes.
- Follow up the stage of restoring activity in the institution after the end of the crisis.
- Monitoring the indicators and results of the crisis and determining the extent of learning from the crises that occurred (Abu Al-Nasr, 2001).

Characteristics of the Crisis Management Team Members:

- Creativity and innovation, i.e. thinking about what is not usually thought, and thus we offer a number of alternatives and develop detailed scenarios for the crisis, and it must have the ability to include new ideas and suggestions.
- The ability to make quick, clear and effective decisions. He has a long and varied experience where they have practiced technical details on an actual level.
- He must have personal qualities such as the ability to be calm and knowledgeable (Harved, 2004, p.6).
- He does not have a responsibility to prevent the crisis and stop it from the beginning by defining the roles accurately (Keeling, 2000, p.40).

Composition of the Crisis Management Team: The university organization identifies the members of the crisis management team, attaches the names of the team cadres to all university employees, and determines the means of contacting them before events impose themselves and reveal risks. The crisis management team consists of the following:

- **Head (Leader) Of The Team:** He must be a strong person with wide authority and the ability to direct financial and human resources in the best and shortest ways, along with creativity and innovation (Abbas, 2004, P: 68) and he must have the ability to bear the pressures that the crisis and the ability On dealing with individual and behavioral failures of individuals and maintaining group cohesion, his role is a pivotal role where all communications begin and end at a time of crisis, as leadership is a challenge to crises.
- **A Legal Specialist:** When a crisis occurs, it is necessary to have a person with a legal background, whether from within the university organization or from outside it, as he helps the administration to review the crisis plan and determine what statements and statements should be issued. Controls the actions of workers in times of crisis, and the second is the direction of deciding the legal results and entitlement to compensation and insurances, so he must have extensive experience with the laws (El Hamlawy and Shoman, 2002, P: 159).
- **Public Relations Specialist:** There must be a voice that expresses the university organization during the crisis, presents the true form of the crisis and the developments that are constantly occurring, knows the needs of reporters who are covering the crisis, holds press conferences, and trains managers who speak in front of the public and the press (Abbas, 2004, P: 73) .
- **Technical Experts:** every crisis has its technical, engineering and practical aspects that must be related to the work of the different departments. Therefore, technicians must participate in crisis management, each of them has distinguished engineering experience as well as receive training in the field of crisis management (El Hamlawy and Shoman, 2002, P: 161)
- **Financial Specialist:** Since crises result in severe financial confusion, therefore, when the crisis occurs, the manager or the financial controller must be sought and be on the lookout for the organization's budget and investments, and the preparation of the future crisis management plan is translated into a financial plan and an estimated budget for which balanced funds are allocated (Abbas, 2004, P: 74).
- **Communications Specialist:** deals with all means of communication, whether wired, wireless, electronic, personal, or any type of communication that has a fundamental and effective role in providing assistance to face the crisis effectively (El Hamlawy and Shoman, 2002, P: 161).
- **Clerks, Assistants, And Workers:** Although they are entrusted with other work and are part-time to manage the crisis, as well as the rest of the cadres, most of them are part-time, but as a result of their meetings and what they plan and decide on training programs on crisis management plans and procedures for their implementation, necessarily requires the presence of an assisting

group of clerks, technicians and assistants who are entrusted with recording sessions' lectures and programs Training (Abbas, 2004, P: 78)

Responsibilities and Roles of the Crisis Management Team:

- **Pre-Crisis Period:** in which the crisis management team anticipates the imminence of the crisis or senses its occurrence as soon as possible through modern information systems and early warning, as well as preparing periodic follow-up reports (Keeling, 2000, p.41), and in this step scenarios are also prepared to determine How can the crisis occur and the steps it is going through, making the best scenario and anticipating the worst scenario (Ibrahim, 2002, P: 43).
- **During The Crisis:** the crisis management team holds the crisis committee meeting as soon as possible for cooperation, mutual support and mutual trust, providing an atmosphere of creativity and innovation, studying the bad conditions, and mobilizing the resources required to confront the crisis and containing its damage, as well as the actual implementation of the plans developed to confront the crisis (Beamish, 2003, p .22).
- **Post-Crisis Period:** At this stage, the crisis management team announces the end of the crisis, and this step is often neglected, making university employees in a state of ambiguity, which leads to the spread of rumors (Keeling, 2000, p.41), and it is important that the experience is evaluated for benefit From them in the future so that crises can be prevented or confronted in the future efficiently and effectively and in a less time wise manner, as well as rebuilding scenarios, designing an early warning system and developing a new strategy (Abu Al-Nasr, 2001, P:395).

Through the previous presentation, we saw how the crisis is the danger that threatens the organization and prevents it from achieving its goals. We differentiate between the crisis and the concepts that cause a lot of overlap, then we exposed their characteristics, causes, types and stages.

We also presented the crisis management method, and the difference between it and the crisis management method was clarified, and we presented the crisis management processes, planning, communication, information and decision-making and the role of each in crisis management, as well as the formation and role of the crisis management team and its importance to the organization at the time of its crisis, and accordingly, the picture became clear about the crisis and its management style. And how the theoretical studies dealt with it, but what we lack is how to implement and how the university organizations that dealt with and applied this thought are four American universities: University of California San Francisco, Florida State University, Texas University and Harvard University.

Methodology and Procedures:

According to the objectives of the research, the researchers relied on the descriptive analytical approach in dealing with the research problem, reaching the results and proposing appropriate recommendations to treat the problem by extrapolating the literature of previous studies related to the topic of the research.

First: Type and Sources of Data: In light of the identification of the problem and the research variables, the data that was relied upon in achieving the research objectives can be identified as follows:

1. **Secondary Data:** Some of the recorded and published secondary variables related to crisis management in the ceramic sector have been relied upon. The most important of these data can be summarized as follows:
 - The number of ceramic sector companies in the tenth of Ramadan.
 - A statement about the crises faced by the companies.
- For all the previous secondary data, the researchers relied on:
- Arab and foreign reports and published and unpublished research related to the research topic.
 - Periodicals, bulletins, reports and various statistics.
 - Theses and previous studies published online.
2. **Initial Data:** The primary data necessary for research was collected from companies through the survey method, and the opinions and attitudes of employees in the companies were relied upon to obtain the primary data that served the research requirements.

Second- Study Population: The study population consists of all members of the senior management, as well as those working in the ceramic industry sector in the Tenth of Ramadan City.

Third- Study Sample: The researchers relied on the stratified random sample in each of the study categories individually (the senior management category - the workers category). The researchers distributed the sample using the proportional distribution as shown. The researchers relied on the tables of statistical samples (1) at a confidence level of 95% And an allowable error in the estimation is within 5%, and the percentage of the phenomenon in the community = 0.50, the sample size for the senior management category was = 187, while the sample size for the workers category = 377, and the following is the distribution of the sample and the different response rates in the study categories:

Table 1: the sample distribution and the percentage of the different responses in the study groups

The Company's Name		Community Size	Sample Volume	Correct Responses	Response Rate%
Cleopatra Group	Senior Management	116	60	55	%91.6
	Workers	6233	128	115	%89.8
Eldorard	Senior Management	42	22	20	%90.9
	Workers	2216	45	39	%86.6
Fancy	Senior Management	33	17	16	%94.1
	Workers	1780	36	30	%83.3
the prince	Senior Management	79	41	38	%92.6
	Workers	3614	73	64	%87.6
Al-Rajaa	Senior Management	90	47	46	%97.8
	Workers	4818	95	80	%84.2
Total	Senior Management	360	187	175	%93.58
	Workers	18661	377	328	%87

Statistical analysis of the results of the field study:

Validity and reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha coefficient): The reliability coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) was calculated for the survey questions in each category of the study, in order to examine the reliability of the questionnaire questions and to examine the extent to which these questions could be relied upon in the analysis. The values of the validity and reliability coefficients were in the following tables:

Table 2: Honesty and Constancy Coefficients for the Senior Management Category

Field Name	Number Of Items	Cronbach's Alpha coefficient	Stability Coefficients
Trend Change Strategy	4	0.734	0.856
Crisis Division Strategy	4	0.781	0.883
Crisis Containment Strategy	4	0.776	0.880
Crisis Management Strategy	4	0.829	0.910
Signal Stage And Early Warning	4	0.905	0.951
Preparedness And Prevention Phase	4	0.859	0.926
Damage Containment Phase	4	0.841	0.917
Recovery Phase	4	0.799	0.893
Learning Phase	4	0.803	0.896

From the previous table, it is clear that the validity and reliability coefficients are acceptable for the questionnaire as a whole, because all the value of the validity and reliability coefficients exceeded (0.5) in the category of senior management members. Of the variables under study.

Table 3: Honesty and reliability coefficients for the category of workers

Field Name	Number Of Items	Cronbach's Alpha coefficient	Stability Coefficients
Trend Change Strategy	4	0.787	0.887
Crisis Division Strategy	4	0.862	0.928
Crisis Containment Strategy	4	0.743	0.861
Crisis Management Strategy	4	0.715	0.845
Signal Stage And Early Warning	4	0.721	0.849
Preparedness And Prevention Phase	4	0.697	0.834
Damage Containment Phase	4	0.723	0.850
Recovery Phase	4	0.801	0.894
Learning Phase	4	0.842	0.917

From the previous table, it is clear that the validity and reliability coefficients are acceptable for the questionnaire as a whole, because all the value of the validity and reliability coefficients exceeded (0.5) in the category of workers and therefore it can be said that they are coefficients of good significance for research purposes, and therefore they can be relied upon in the analysis without excluding any element of the variables place of study.

Descriptive Statistics for the Results of the Field Study: The following is a presentation of the descriptive statistics results in the two study categories, where the researchers relied on the weighted arithmetic mean, standard deviation, as well as the relative importance as a reflection of the weighted average value in the form of a percentage.

1- Analysis Of The Answers Of Senior Management Category:**First- The Company's Crisis Management Strategies:****Table 4:** Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, regarding the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The crises experienced by the company had an impact on the direction of the company's work performance.	3.79	0.9	%75.9	The Third
2.	The company's management deals with crises based on options appropriate to their severity.	4.10	0.82	%82.1	The First
3.	The company's management uses a strategy to change direction when faced with uncertain crises.	3.97	0.89	%79.9	The Second
4.	The strategy of changing direction has a positive impact on the expected performance of the company.	3.75	0.93	%75.1	The Fourth

With regard to the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The element of the company's management deals with crises based on the appropriate options for their severity, with a relative importance of 82.1% and a standard deviation of 0.82. The element came in the second order. The company's management uses a strategy to change direction when faced with unclear crises With a relative importance of 79.9% and a standard deviation of 0.89, while in the last order came the element of the strategy to change the direction of a positive impact on the expected performance of the company with a relative importance of 75.1% and a standard deviation of 0.93. In general, all the relative importance values exceeded 70%, which means the approval of the study sample from the members of the senior management clearly that all those elements that express the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis are well applied in the companies under study.

Table 5: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, regarding the crisis division strategy

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management has sufficient information about the nature of the crisis it is facing.	3.57	0.96	%71.5	The Fourth
2.	The company's management conducts the necessary studies to determine the conflicting interests causing the crisis	4.01	0.86	%80.3	The First
3.	The management of the company relies on specialists in the division and segmentation of the crisis.	4	0.88	%80.1	The Second
4.	The company is usually able to successfully segment the crisis.	3.93	0.93	%78.7	The Third

With regard to the variable of the crisis division strategy, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The company management conducts the necessary studies to determine the conflicting interests that cause the crisis, with a relative importance of 80.3% and a standard deviation of 0.86. It amounted to 80.1% and a standard deviation of 0.88, while in the last rank came the element the company's management possesses sufficient information about the nature of the crisis it is facing with a relative importance of 71.5% and a standard deviation of 0.96. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 70%, which means the approval of the study sample from the members of the senior management in a way it is clear that all those elements that express the strategy of dividing the crisis are clearly applied in the ceramic industry companies.

Table 6: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, regarding the crisis containment strategy

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management is based on the adoption of specialized teams from within to contain the crisis.	4.07	0.84	%81.4	The Second
2.	Over the past years, the company was able to successfully contain crises.	4.36	0.83	%87.2	The First
3.	The company is negotiating with the cause of the crisis to contain it.	3.69	0.85	%73.8	The Fourth
4.	Employees are making the necessary efforts to help contain the crisis.	3.93	0.86	%78.6	The Third

With regard to the crisis containment strategy, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The element was able to successfully contain the crises during the previous years, with a relative importance of 87.2% and a standard deviation of 0.83. In the second place came the element. The company's management relies on the adoption of specialized teams from within to contain

the crisis with relative importance It amounted to 81.4% and a standard deviation of 0.84, while in the last order came the element. The company is negotiating with the cause of the crisis because it contains a relative importance of 73.8% and a standard deviation of 0.85. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 70%, which means that the study sample of senior management members clearly agreed that all of these elements that express the crisis containment strategy are widely applied in the ceramics industry.

Table 7: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, with regard to the strategy for dealing with the crisis

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management is able to analyze the contents and content of the crisis and deal with it.	4.15	0.7	%83.1	The Third
2.	The company's management resorts to acknowledging the existence of the crisis initially to ensure that it is addressed.	4.5	0.62	%90.1	The First
3.	The company establishes temporary alliances with the elements causing the crisis in order to address it.	3.86	0.77	%77.2	The Fourth
4.	The company believes that the crisis management strategy is an appropriate solution to confront the crisis	4.47	0.64	%89.4	The Second

With regard to the crisis management strategy, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The company's management resorts to acknowledging the existence of the crisis initially to ensure that it is dealt with with a relative importance of 90.1% and a standard deviation of 0.62. In the second order came the element. The company sees that the crisis management strategy is an appropriate solution to confronting the crisis with importance a relative amount of 89.4% and a standard deviation of 0.64, while in the last order came the element. The company establishes temporary alliances with the elements causing the crisis in order to treat them with a relative importance of 77.2% and a standard deviation of 0.77. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 70%, which means the approval of the study sample from the members the senior management clearly stated that all those elements that express the crisis management strategy are well implemented in the ceramic industry companies.

Second- The Stages of the Crisis:

Table 8: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents from the senior management category with regard to the early warning stage

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company has a special department whose task is to monitor indicators of crises.	4.34	0.73	%86.9	The Fourth
2.	The company's senior management pays attention to monitoring indicators of crises	4.58	0.64	%91.6	The First
3.	I feel that there is an interest in the company in collecting and detecting danger signs, which may be indicative of a crisis.	4.56	0.64	%91.3	The Second
4.	The company's work environment is comprehensively surveyed to identify indicators of the possibility of a crisis occurring.	4.43	0.71	%88.7	The Third

With regard to the stage of signals and early warning of the crisis, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order, the element. The senior management of the company pays attention to monitoring the indicators of the occurrence of crises with a relative importance of 91.6% and a standard deviation of 0.64. In the second order came the element I feel that there is an interest in the company in collecting and discovering danger signs, Which may be an indicator of the occurrence of the crisis, with a relative importance of 91.3% and a standard deviation of 0.64, while in the last order came the element that the company has a special department whose tasks are to monitor indicators of the occurrence of crises with a relative importance of 86.9% and a standard deviation of 0.73. In general, all values of relative importance exceed 80% of what it means the clear approval of the study sample from the members of the senior management that all those elements that express the stage of warning and early detection of the crisis are widely applied in the ceramic industry companies.

Table 9: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, with regard to the stage of preparedness and prevention

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	Various different teams are formed to solve many potential crises in the company.	3.91	0.81	%78.2	The Third
2.	Investigate mock experiments to deal with potential crises.	3.57	0.81	%71.5	The Fourth

3.	Sufficient and ready-made programs and plans for crisis management are available in the company.	4.07	0.74	%81.4	The Second
4.	There are administrative instructions that specify how and procedures to deal with potential crises.	4.42	0.71	%88.4	The First

With regard to the stage of preparedness and prevention, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The element. There are administrative instructions that specify how and procedures for dealing with potential crises with a relative importance of 88.4% and a standard deviation of 0.71. In the second order came the element Adequate and ready programs and plans are available for crisis management in the company with a relative importance of % 81.4 and a standard deviation of 0.74, while in the last rank, the element investigated mock experiments to deal with potential crises with a relative importance of 71.5% and a standard deviation of 0.81. In general, all the relative importance values exceeded 70%, which means that the study sample of senior management members clearly agreed that all of these Elements that express readiness and prevention are properly present in the ceramics industry.

Table 10: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, regarding the stage of damage containment

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The time factor is taken into account when dealing with crises and with appropriate accuracy.	4.11	0.78	%82.3	The Third
2.	The crisis is controlled when it occurs and its spread and continuation are limited in an appropriate period of time.	4.05	0.79	%80.9	The Fourth
3.	The contingency plan that minimizes and limits the damage caused by the crisis has been used efficiently.	4.48	0.75	%89.7	The Second
4.	Communication operations investigate an accurate and rapid manner to ascertain the extent of the damage caused or caused by the crisis.	4.52	0.72	%90.5	The First

With regard to the damage containment stage, the relative importance came in the first order. The element investigated the communication processes in an accurate and rapid form to ascertain the extent of the damage caused or caused by the crisis, with a relative importance of 90.5% and a standard deviation of 0.72. In the second order, the element was used. The emergency plan that reduces and limits of the damage caused by the crisis efficiently, with a relative importance of 89.7% and a standard deviation of 0.75, while in the last order came the element. The crisis is controlled when it occurs and the spread and continuation of the crisis is limited in an appropriate period of time with a relative importance of 80.9% and a standard deviation of 0.79. In general, all values of the relative importance exceed 80% which means the unanimity of the study sample from the members of the senior management clearly that all those elements that express the containment of the damage caused by the crisis are applied very clearly in the ceramic industry companies.

Table 11: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, with regard to the stage of recovery of activity

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company maintains the necessary procedures to continue its normal activities without any delay.	4.19	0.74	%83.9	The First
2.	The company's management is identifying the necessary needs for the various sites affected by the crisis to address the effects of the crisis and restore normal activity.	4.15	0.76	%83.1	The Second
3.	Merging with other companies to strengthen the company to face crises.	3.5	0.78	%70.1	The Fourth
4.	The company's management has learned to take all necessary measures to mitigate the effects of the crisis and limit its continued occurrence.	4.07	0.78	%81.5	The Third

With regard to the variable of restoring activity, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order, the element. The company maintains the necessary procedures to continue the normal activities without any delay, with a relative importance of 83.9% and a standard deviation of 0.74. In the second place is the element. The company's management determines the necessary needs for the various sites affected by the crisis to address The effects of the crisis and the restoration of normal activity with a relative importance of 83.1% and a standard deviation of 0.76, while in the last arrangement came the element of merging with other companies to strengthen the company to face crises with a relative importance of 70.1% and a standard deviation of 0.78. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 70%, which means the approval of the study sample Members of the senior management clearly stated that all those elements that express the recovery of activity are largely present in the ceramic industry companies.

Table 12: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the senior management category, with regard to the education stage

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management effectively derives lessons, effects, and lessons from the crises it faced previously, in an attempt to benefit from them in the future.	4.28	0.72	%85.6	The Second
2.	The company's management evaluates previous crisis management plans and programs with the intention of developing and improving them in order to deal with future crises.	4.34	0.73	%86.8	The First
3.	The company's management integrates the lessons learned from the shortcomings and gaps in the previous plans with great accuracy into the plans for future crises.	4.12	0.76	%82.4	The Third
4.	Preparing, collecting and distributing information with high transparency.	4.02	0.77	%80.5	The Fourth

With regard to the education stage, the relative importance came in the first order. The company's management evaluates previous crisis management plans and programs with a view to developing and improving them in order to deal with future crises, with a relative importance of 86.8% and a standard deviation of 0.73. The company's management effectively extracts lessons in the second order. And the effects and lessons from the crises that it faced previously in an attempt to benefit from it in the future with a relative importance of 85.6% and a standard deviation of 0.72, while in the last order came the element of preparing, collecting and distributing information with high transparency, with a relative importance of 80.5% and a standard deviation of 0.77. In general, all values of the relative importance were more than 80% which means that the study sample from the members of the senior management clearly agreed that all those elements that express education are applied very clearly in the ceramic industry companies.

2- Analysis Of The Answers Of The Employees Category:

First- The Company's Crisis Management Strategies:

Table 13: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, including the category of workers, regarding the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The crises experienced by the company had an impact on the direction of the company's work performance.	3.29	0.96	%65.9	The Fourth
2.	The company's management deals with crises based on options appropriate to their severity.	3.41	0.94	%68.3	The Third
3.	The company's management uses a strategy to change direction when faced with uncertain crises.	3.56	0.94	%71.2	The Second
4.	The strategy of changing direction has a positive impact on the expected performance of the company.	3.73	0.92	%74.6	The First

With regard to the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The element of the strategy of changing direction has a positive impact on the expected performance of the company, with a relative importance of 74.6% and a standard deviation of 0.92. In the second order came the element. The company's management uses a directional change strategy when faced with unclear crises of importance A relative value of 71.2% and a standard deviation of 0.94, while in the last rank the element that the crises experienced by the company had an impact on the direction of the company's work performance with a relative importance of 65.9% and a standard deviation of 0.96 came in general all the relative importance values exceed 65%, which means the approval of the study sample Of the employees of the companies under study, on average, all of those elements that express the use of the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis by the senior management are applied in a non-significant manner.

Table 14: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, including the category of workers, regarding the strategy of dividing the crisis

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management has sufficient information about the nature of the crisis it is facing.	3.50	1.02	%70.1	The Fourth
2.	The company's management conducts the necessary studies to determine the conflicting interests causing the crisis	3.82	0.95	%76.4	The Second
3.	The management of the company relies on specialists in the division and segmentation of the crisis.	3.86	0.94	%77.3	The First

4.	The company is usually able to successfully segment the crisis.	3.58	0.99	%71.6	The Third
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With regard to the strategy of dividing the crisis, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The company's management relies on specialists in dividing and segmenting the crisis with a relative importance of 77.3% and a standard deviation of 0.94. In the second order came the element. The company's management conducts the necessary studies to determine the conflicting interests that cause the crisis with a relative importance that amounted to 76.4% and a standard deviation of 0.95, while in the last rank the company management possesses sufficient information about the nature of the crisis it is facing with a relative importance of 70.1% and a standard deviation of 1.02. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 70%, which means that the study sample of workers in the companies under study agreed in general somewhat significant that all those elements that express the use of the crisis division strategy by the top management are largely applied.

Table 15: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, including the category of workers, regarding the crisis containment strategy

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management is based on the adoption of specialized teams from within to contain the crisis.	4.20	0.91	%84.1	The Second
2.	Over the past years, the company was able to successfully contain crises.	4.26	0.89	%85.3	The First
3.	The company is negotiating with the cause of the crisis to contain it.	3.95	0.99	%79.1	The Fourth
4.	Employees are making the necessary efforts to help contain the crisis.	4.14	0.93	%82.9	The Third

With regard to the crisis containment strategy, it came in the order of relative importance in the first place, the element. The company was able, through the previous years, to successfully contain crises with a relative importance of 85.3% and a standard deviation of 0.89. It amounted to 84.1% and a standard deviation of 0.91, while in the last order came the element. The company is negotiating with the cause of the crisis because it contains a relative importance of 79.1% and a standard deviation of 0.99. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 75%, which means that the study sample of workers in the companies under study largely agreed on All those elements that express the use of the crisis containment strategy by the senior management are widely applied.

Table 16: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, including the category of workers, regarding the strategy for dealing with the crisis

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management is able to analyze the contents and content of the crisis and deal with it.	4.06	0.98	%81.3	The First
2.	The company's management resorts to acknowledging the existence of the crisis initially to ensure that it is addressed.	3.46	1.09	%69.2	The Fourth
3.	The company establishes temporary alliances with the elements causing the crisis in order to address it.	3.71	1.01	%74.3	The Second
4.	The company believes that the crisis management strategy is an appropriate solution to confront the crisis	3.64	1.03	%72.9	The Third

With regard to the crisis management strategy, the relative importance came in the first order, the element of the company's management is able to analyze the contents and content of the crisis and deal with it, with a relative importance of 81.3% and a standard deviation of 0.98. A relative value of 74.3% and a standard deviation of 1.01, while in the last arrangement the company's management resort to recognizing the existence of the crisis in principle to ensure that it is treated with a relative importance of 69.2% and a standard deviation of 1.09. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 65%, which means the approval of the study sample of workers In the companies under study in an average way, all those elements that express the use of the crisis management strategy by the senior management are applied in a small way, which indicates that the senior management must take into account that dimension from the point of view of the workers.

Second- The Stages of the Crisis:

Table 17: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, including the category of workers, regarding the early warning stage

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company has a special department whose task is to monitor indicators of crises.	3.91	0.91	%78.2	The Fourth
2.	The company's senior management pays attention to monitoring indicators of crises	4.24	0.87	%84.9	The Second

3.	I feel that there is an interest in the company in collecting and detecting danger signs, which may be indicative of a crisis.	4.26	0.87	%85.3	The First
4.	The company's work environment is comprehensively surveyed to identify indicators of the possibility of a crisis occurring.	3.95	0.89	%79.1	The Third

Regarding the stage of signals and early warning, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The element I feel that there is an interest in the company in collecting and discovering danger signs, which may be indicative of the occurrence of the crisis, with a relative importance of 85.3% and a standard deviation of 0.87. In the second order, the element is taken over by the senior management of the company. An interest in monitoring the indicators of the occurrence of crises with a relative importance of 84.9% and a standard deviation of 0.87, while in the last order came the element that the company has a special department whose tasks are to monitor the indicators of the occurrence of crises with a relative importance of 78.2% and a standard deviation of 0.91. In general, all values of relative importance exceed 75%, which means approval the study sample is largely from the employees of the companies under study that all those elements that express the early warning of the crisis by the senior management are widely applied.

Table 18: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, including the category of workers, with regard to the stage of preparedness and prevention

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	Various different teams are formed to solve many potential crises in the company.	4.10	0.98	%82.1	The First
2.	Investigate mock experiments to deal with potential crises.	3.26	1.13	%65.3	The Fourth
3.	Sufficient and ready-made programs and plans for crisis management are available in the company.	3.60	1.03	%72.1	The Third
4.	There are administrative instructions that specify how and procedures to deal with potential crises.	3.97	1.01	%79.4	The Second

With regard to the stage of preparedness and prevention, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order. The element is formed different and multiple teams to solve many potential crises in the company with a relative importance of 82.1% and a standard deviation of 1.01 and came in the second order of the element There are administrative instructions specifying how and procedures for dealing with potential crises with importance A relative value of 79.4% and a standard deviation of 1.01, while in the last order came the element of investigation of dummy experiments to deal with potential crises with a relative importance of 65.3% and a standard deviation of 1.13. In general, all the relative importance values exceed 65%, which means that the study sample of workers in the companies under study agrees in an average way However, all those elements that express the readiness and prevention of the crisis by the senior management are not applied to a large extent.

Table 19: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the category of workers, regarding the stage of damage containment

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The time factor is taken into account when dealing with crises and with appropriate accuracy.	3.87	1.01	%77.4	The Second
2.	The crisis is controlled when it occurs and its spread and continuation are limited in an appropriate period of time.	3.60	1.09	%72.1	The Third
3.	The contingency plan that minimizes and limits the damage caused by the crisis has been used efficiently.	3.24	1.12	%64.9	The Fourth
4.	Communication operations investigate an accurate and rapid manner to ascertain the extent of the damage caused or caused by the crisis.	4.04	0.99	%80.8	The First

With regard to the damage containment stage, the relative importance came in the first order. The element investigated the communication processes in an accurate and rapid way to ascertain the extent of the damage caused or caused by the crisis, with a relative importance of 80.8% and a standard deviation of 0.99. In the second order came the element the time factor is taken when dealing with crises taking into account and with appropriate accuracy with a relative importance of 77.4% and a standard deviation of 1.01, while in the last order came the element. The emergency plan that reduces and limits the damage caused by the crisis was used efficiently with a relative importance of 64.9% and a standard deviation of 1.12. In general, all values of the relative importance exceed 65% of what it means the average agreement of the study sample of the employees of the companies under study that all those elements that express the severity of the damages caused by the senior management are clearly not applied.

Table 20: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, the category of workers, regarding the stage of recovery

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company maintains the necessary procedures to continue its normal activities without any delay.	4.03	0.91	%80.6	The First
2.	The company's management is identifying the necessary needs for the various sites affected by the crisis to address the effects of the crisis and restore normal activity.	3.69	0.93	%73.9	The Second
3.	Merging with other companies to strengthen the company to face crises.	3.57	0.99	%71.4	The Third
4.	The company's management has learned to take all necessary measures to mitigate the effects of the crisis and limit its continued occurrence.	3.41	0.98	%68.2	The Fourth

With regard to the stage of restoring activity, it came in the order of relative importance in the first order, the element. The company maintains the necessary procedures to continue the normal activities without any delay, with a relative importance of 80.6% and a standard deviation of 0.91. In the second order is the element. The company's management determines the necessary needs for the various sites affected by the crisis to address The effects of the crisis and the restoration of normal activity with a relative importance of 73.9% and a standard deviation of 0.93 while in the last order came the element of learning the company's management to take all necessary measures to mitigate the effects of the crisis and limit its continuation of its occurrence with a relative importance of 68.2% and a standard deviation of 0.98 and came in general all the values of relative importance It exceeded 65%, which means that the study sample of employees of the companies under study agreed on an average that all those elements that express the use of restoring activity by senior management are applied in a small way.

Table 21: Statistical analysis of the answers of the respondents, including the category of workers, with regard to the stage of education

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company's management effectively derives lessons, effects, and lessons from the crises it faced previously, in an attempt to benefit from them in the future.	3.66	0.97	%73.2	The First
2.	The company's management evaluates previous crisis management plans and programs with the intention of developing and improving them in order to deal with future crises.	3.5	0.98	%70.1	The Second
3.	The company's management integrates the lessons learned from the shortcomings and gaps in the previous plans with great accuracy into the plans for future crises.	3.29	1.11	%65.9	The Fourth
4.	Preparing, collecting and distributing information with high transparency.	3.42	1.03	%68.4	The Third

With regard to the education stage, the relative importance came in the first order. The company's management effectively derives lessons, effects and lessons from the crises it faced previously in an attempt to benefit from them in the future, with a relative importance of 73.2% and a standard deviation of 0.97. In the second order came the element. The company's management evaluates plans and programs managing previous crises with the intention of developing and improving them in order to deal with future crises with a relative importance of 70.1% and a standard deviation of 0.98, while the last item came in the last order. The company's management integrates lessons learned from the shortcomings and gaps in previous plans with high accuracy in future crisis plans with a relative importance of 65.9% and a deviation Standards 1.11 In general, all the relative importance values exceed 65%, which means that the study sample of employees in the companies under study agrees in an average way that all those elements that express education from the top management are applied inappropriately.

Conclusions

After analyzing, interpreting and discussing the questions, the following results were reached, and the presentation of these results was taken into account according to the research variables, as it becomes clear:

1. The results clearly showed the approval of the study sample from the members of the senior management that all of those elements of crisis management strategies (the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis, the strategy of dividing the crisis, the strategy of containing the crisis, the strategy of dealing with the crisis) are well applied in the ceramic companies under study.
2. The results revealed the unanimity of the study sample from the members of the senior management clearly that all the elements that express the stages of the crisis (the stage of signals and early warning, the stage of preparedness and prevention, the stage of containing the crisis, the stage of recovery of activity, the stage of learning) are clearly applied in the ceramic companies under study.

3. The results of the study confirmed the approval of the study sample of company employees, on average, on the strategy of changing the direction of the crisis and that it was applied in a non-significant manner
4. The results showed that the study sample of workers agreed to a certain extent on the (crisis division strategy, crisis containment strategy) and that it was widely applied.
5. The results of the study confirmed the approval of the study sample of workers, on average, on the elements of the crisis management strategy, and that it was applied in a non-significant manner.
6. The results of the study confirmed that the study sample of workers agreed largely on the elements of the signaling and early warning stage and that they were applied in a non-significant manner.
7. The results of the study showed that the study sample of workers agreed on average on the elements of the preparedness and prevention stage and that they were applied in a small way.
8. The results of the study revealed that the study sample of workers agreed on average (the stage of damage containment, the stage of restoring your activity, the stage of learning) and that it was applied in an unclear and inappropriate manner.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, there are a set of recommendations according to the research variables, as follows:

First: Recommendations for Crisis Management Strategies:

- Businesses must be convinced of the importance and usefulness of having a crisis plan.
- Work on developing basic steps for the crisis planning process.
- Formation and selection of a crisis management team.
- Work on analyzing the sources and effects of crises.
- The necessity of dealing with crises by working with plans.
- Training and preparing individuals to perform efficiently and effectively in crisis situations.
- Using the wisdom and experience of the crisis management team and the most efficient workers, and coordinating between them to reduce and avoid the effects of the crisis.

Second: Recommendations for the stages of the crisis:

A. Recommendations For The Early Warning Signs Detection Phase:

- The need to establish a crisis management unit in the organizational structure of companies and to seek the assistance of an efficient staff.
- Paying attention to the continuous monitoring and detection of early warning signals and their capture.
- Work on assembling efforts to discover and analyze the indicators of the occurrence of the crisis and study all the variables of the internal and external work environment of the company to identify the indicators of the possibility of a crisis as an introduction to an early warning system in ceramic companies that is compatible with the indicators of events that may cause the crisis to occur to reduce its appearance before it occurs and this The best way to manage a crisis.

B. Recommendations for the preparedness and prevention phase:

- Pooling efforts to reduce the continuation of the crisis in its early stages and to manage it effectively.
- Companies developing a written and comprehensive plan to deal with potential crises in the future.
- Forming an efficient and effective crisis management team and providing the necessary support to it.
- The need for an effective communication system linking the crisis management team, senior management, and workers at all functional levels.
- Providing distinctive and specialized training programs in crisis management.

C. Recommendations for the damage containment phase:

- Emphasizing the protection of people and property as an important priority during crises.
- Providing all the necessary human, financial, informational and material resources to contain the crisis.
- Providing good means of communication between the different administrative levels and the crisis management team.

D. Recommendations for the recovery phase:

- Work to determine the necessary needs for the sites affected by crises in order to provide the necessary care, compensation and rewards for those affected by the occurrence of the crisis.
- Improving companies' use and provision of media during crises.
- Emphasis on the continuation of production lines to work without delay and the provision of raw materials for them.
- Restore the company's normal situation as soon as possible so as not to lose customers.

E. Recommendations for the Learning phase:

- Interest in drawing lessons and lessons from the crises that have been faced.

- Work on evaluating previous crisis management plans and programs in order to develop and improve them in order to deal with future crises.
- Preparing training programs to monitor the development of crisis management science.

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